

Building the collective at times of precarity:
precarious labour and its countermovements

Data Management Plan

Version 1.1

Deliverable 2.1

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Introduction

COLLECTITUDE is a Horizon 2020 project and integrates the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), requiring the provision of a continuously updated Data Management Plan (DMP).

The purpose of the DMP is to provide an overview of the data to be collected, processed and generated by project COLLECTITUDE and to describe the data management life cycle, aiming at making research data *FAIR – findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable* (EC, 2016). Open access to data and publications under H2020 contributes to improving transparency and integrity of the scientific process and to building on previous research results, promoting greater efficiency, fostering innovation and boosting the benefits of public investment in research.

COLLECTITUDE research outputs (publications, data, and other outputs) will be managed in line with the FAIR principles to facilitate their re-use in the future. As per the Grant Agreement, the project shall ensure open access to all scientific publications relating to its results and open access to research data generated in the action (statistics, observations from fieldwork, interviews' content analysis, images, etc.).

This document is the first version of the DMP, which is intended to be further developed as the implementation of the project progresses. A final, updated version will be provided before the end of the action.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
CC	Creative Commons
CERN	European Laboratory for Particle Physics
DCMI	Dublin Core™ Metadata Initiative
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
IF	Individual Fellowship
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PID	Persistent and unique Identifier
QDA	Qualitative Data Analysis
V	Version
WP	Work Package

1. Data Summary

The COLLECTITUDE project aims to analyse current and future transformations in the world of work at times of precarity, by researching the relationship between precarisation, on the one hand, and agency and social change, on the other, developing a new analytical perspective that is able to articulate this double movement and to capture both national and transnational social processes underway. It will address this double movement by focusing on the case of Portugal and by undertaking a comparative analysis of two professional groups that occupy a specific space in current models of capitalism, assuming a set of common trends throughout various countries, while representing two distinct sectors of the workforce: the construction industry, a labour-intensive sector, whose jobs are mostly unskilled, low-wage and insecure; and the arts sector, whose work is highly qualified, though intermittent and often unprotected.

The research requires the collection, processing and storage of a large variety of datasets, both primary and secondary, comprising quantitative and qualitative data. As the data identification and collection activities are still ongoing, the initial DMP provides an incomplete picture of the datasets.

Below is a short summary of the datasets that have been identified for COLLECTITUDE according to each research work package (WP):

WP1. The political economy of precarity:

- Literature report, including a glossary of COLLECTITUDE concepts;
- Datasets with economic, social and political indicators of precarity (Eurostat data, Labour Force Survey, European Working Conditions Survey, data from the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics – INE);
- Raw data from exploratory interviews to key informants;
- Factsheet with the operationalisation of project main variables and indicators;
- Research instruments (interview guides, focus groups guides, field notes template).

WP2. The relationship between the precariousness of work and precarity of livelihoods:

- Observation field notes;
- Raw data from semi-structured interviews (audio and recordings);
- Content analysis of interviews;
- Peer-reviewed scientific paper;

WP3. Collective agency and organisation at times of precarity

- Dataset of press and social media news;
- Content analysis of press and social media news;
- Raw data from focus groups (audio and recordings);
- Content analysis of focus groups;

- Peer-reviewed scientific paper.

WP4. Paths of intervention

- Report to stakeholders;
- Peer-reviewed scientific paper;
- Final analytical matrix;
- Project final report.

A more detailed description of the type and format of data can be found in Annex I.

2. Data Management Policy

The general data management policy of COLLECTITUDE project has been developed in accordance to Horizon 2020 principles on FAIR data (EC, 2016) and the requirements of the ORDP (EC, 2017).

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1. Discoverability of data (metadata provision)

All open data and publications produced in COLLECTITUDE will be identifiable and locatable by means of a Persistent and unique Identifier (PID), whenever possible assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) in order to make content easily and uniquely citable.

Open data and publications are deposited in the COLLECTITUDE default Open Access repository (Zenodo, see 2.2.2) and will be automatically assigned a DOI.

2.1.2. Naming conventions followed

The project will follow a consistent strategy for **naming files**, which reflects the contents of the file and identifies it with a unique identifier, enabling to easily identify, locate and use research data files efficiently and effectively.

According to extended practices to standardise file names, COLLECTITUDE complies with the following general specifications:

- File names should be short but descriptive (<40 characters);
- Use alphanumeric and avoid special characters (such as "/ \ : * < > [] \$ & ~ ! # ? { } ' ^ %);
- Use underscores _ instead of periods or spaces to separate elements in a file name;

- Standardise dates (according to ISO standards: YYYYMMDD);
- Use leading zeros for sequential numbering.

Moreover, file names contain a consistent set of elements in order to easily identify files connected to each data collection event:

<acro>_<type><ID>_<date>_<datatype>_<version>.<extension>

that is:

- Project acronym (i.e. COLLECTITUDE) – compulsory for deliverables and data openly shared;
- Type of document/event/data material (“dataset”, “template”, “DMP”, “interv” for interview, “FG” for focus group, “obs” for observation) – compulsory for all documents;
- ID of the collection event (number) when more than one (e.g. interv01, interv02);
- Date of document or when data were collected (in the ISO8601 format YYYYMMDD) – compulsory for all documents;
- Type of data the file contains when referring to data collection events ("trans" for transcription, "audio" for audio recording, and "image" for photograph, which may require an additional number to differentiate within a set of images or audio files connected to the same collection event);
- File version documents in x_y format, where x is the version number and y is the revision number (e.g. v1_1) – compulsory for internal documents (see 3.1.4);
- File extension (e.g. odt) – compulsory for all files.

Example:

COLLECTITUDE_DMP_20200623_v1_1.pdf

COLLECTITUDE_interv02_20200611_audio.wav

COLLECTITUDE_interv02_20200611_trans.odt

COLLECTITUDE_interv02_20200611_image01.jpg

COLLECTITUDE_interv02_20200611_image02.jpg

Regarding **variable names**, a consistent strategy will also be followed, compliant with the requirements of the software package being used and considering the long-term utility of the variable name to the widest audience of users (ICPST 2010). A systematic approach involves constructing variable names containing a root, a prefix, and possibly a suffix, based on short standard abbreviations to be defined.

2.1.3. Approach towards search keyword – in order to optimize possibilities for re-use

All COLLECTITUDE data and results deposited in a repository will provide search keywords together with their metadata (see 2.1.5). Keywords for open data will be

selected from controlled vocabularies that are suitable for the specific type of the data (see 2.3.3).

Resource to the Humanities and Social Science Electronic Thesaurus (HASSET)¹ will be used for the homogenisation of terms and definitions.

2.1.4. Approach for clear versioning

To keep track of changes, the versioning management of the publications, data, metadata and files in general will be applied at two levels:

- Using version numbers in the file name, indicating any major changes to a file (version) by whole numbers (e.g. v1) and minor changes (revisions) by increasing the decimal figure (e.g. v1_1);
- Including a “Revision History” table inside the file registering the versions history (with information on version, revision, date, description, author).

Additionally, all open data, publications and open source software deposited in the Zenodo repository (see 2.2.2) will use DOI versioning, which enables to easily identify and cite either specific versions of a record or to cite, via a top-level DOI, all the versions of a record.

2.1.5. Standards for metadata creation

Considering the availability of many different metadata standards for different types of data and the difficulty in finding one that fits all purposes, metadata for describing COLLECTITUDE data will be based on a common and minimal catalogue metadata schema for those datasets that are published in public catalogues and data repositories and use data-type specific schema extensions, if necessary.

Default catalogue metadata schema for open data generated by the project deposited in the Zenodo repository² will include the following mandatory fields:

¹ <https://hasset.ukdataservice.ac.uk>

² For the Zenodo deposition metadata domain model, see: <http://developers.Zenodo.org/#representation>.

Attribute	Description
upload_type	Controlled vocabulary: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * publication: Publication * poster: Poster * presentation: Presentation * dataset: Dataset * image: Image * video: Video/Audio * software: Software * lesson: Lesson * other: Other
publication_type (if upload_type is "publication")	Controlled vocabulary: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * annotationcollection: Annotation collection * book: Book * section: Book section * conferencepaper: Conference paper * datamanagementplan: Data management plan * article: Journal article * patent: Patent * preprint: Preprint * deliverable: Project deliverable * milestone: Project milestone * proposal: Proposal * report: Report * softwaredocumentation: Software documentation * taxonomicreatment: Taxonomic treatment * technicalnote: Technical note * thesis: Thesis * workingpaper: Working paper * other: Other
publication_date	Date of publication in ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD). Defaults to current date.
title	Title of deposition.
creators	The creators/authors of the deposition. Each array element is an object with the attributes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * name: Name of creator in the format Family name, Given names * affiliation: Affiliation of creator (optional). * orcid: ORCID identifier of creator (optional).
description	Abstract or description for deposition. Including the text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 841164".
access_right	Controlled vocabulary: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * open: Open Access * embargoed: Embargoed Access * restricted: Restricted Access * closed: Closed Access Defaults to open.
License (if access_right	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0), by default for datasets and non-datasets. The selected license applies to all files in the deposition, but not to

Attribute	Description
is "open" or "embargoed")	the metadata which is licensed under Creative Commons Zero (CC0). Further information about CC licenses is available at https://creativecommons.org/about/ccllicenses/
embargo_date (if access_right is "embargoed")	When the deposited files will be made automatically made publicly available by the system. Defaults to current date.
access_conditions (if access_right is "restricted")	Specify the conditions under which users may be granted access to the uploaded files. Users requesting access will be asked to justify how they fulfil the conditions. Based on the justification, access may be granted or denied.
doi	Digital Object Identifier assigned by the DOI registrant (publisher or Zenodo)
keywords	Mandatory Keywords for the project - "Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action"; "Collectitude" – and Free form keywords for this deposition.
related_identifiers (if any)	Persistent identifiers of related publications and datasets. Supported identifiers include: DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs and URLs.
contributors	The contributors of the deposition (e.g. editors, funders, etc.). Each array element is an object with the attributes: * name: Name of creator in the format Family name, Given names * type: Contributor type. Controlled vocabulary (ContactPerson, DataCollector, DataCurator, DataManager, Distributor, Editor, Funder, HostingInstitution, Producer, ProjectLeader, ProjectManager, ProjectMember, RegistrationAgency, RegistrationAuthority, RelatedPerson, Researcher, ResearchGroup, RightsHolder, Supervisor, Sponsor, WorkPackageLeader, Other) Include the funder and action: European Commission/ Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action
communities	List of communities the deposition to appears in (https://zenodo.org/communities/collectitude/)
grants	Funder (European Commission) DOI prefix and Grand ID: 10.13039/501100000780::841164

This minimal metadata schema is compatible with the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) for describing data from the social, behavioural, and economic sciences³ and with the Dublin Core metadata standard – DCMI⁴.

³ <https://ddialliance.org>

⁴ <http://dublincore.org>

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1. Data that will be made openly available as the default

The COLLECTITUDE project will generate different types of **data**, corresponding to different access policies (see Annex I for a detailed data inventory and respective access rights):

- Third-party datasets originate mainly from public sources that are authorised for use in research (Eurostat data, Labour Force Survey, European Working Conditions Survey, data from the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics – INE). Such data will be made open as long as any of the underlying data is open too.
- Primary qualitative data from the project's different data collection events (interviews, focus groups and participant observation) may disclose the identity of research participants, even if anonymised, and therefore the raw data (audio recordings, full interview and focus groups transcripts, field notes) will be kept closed by default. Only the datasets resulting from the qualitative data analysis will be made open, as long as they do not contain identifiable information and their publication does not pose privacy and ethical risks, applying the principle 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'.
- Non-public research data will be archived at the repository using a restricted access option.

In addition, any **scientific publications** from COLLECTITUDE will be made available as open access (in green or gold open access journals, see 2.2.2).

2.2.2. How the data will be made available

Open research outputs (publications, data, and other outputs) will be made available by deposition in a public (research data) repository (see 2.2.6), according to the 'Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020' (EC, 2017) and complying with the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), so that they are available in digital form for access and use free of charge.

Providing **open access to scientific publications** will be ensured by submitting to journals that allow *green open access* (self-archiving) or *gold open access* (open access by the scientific publisher), and by adopting the following procedures:

- deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications (Zenodo and RCAAP, see 2.2.6), even where 'gold' open access publishing is chosen to ensure that the article is preserved in the long term;
- deposit in Zenodo the research data needed to validate the results presented in the scientific publications;

- ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to the deposited publications — via the repository — at the latest:
 - o on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - o within twelve months of publication in any other case;
- ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

Providing **open access to research data** will be ensured by the following procedures:

- deposit in the project default data repository (Zenodo) and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - o the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible (see 2.4.2), and
 - o other data (such as methodology, protocols, standards used to collect the data, and associated metadata), before the submission of the final project report (28 February 2022).
- provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the results, such as workflows, models, software (where possible, providing the tools and instruments themselves).

As soon as they are available, research outputs will be further announced on the project website (<https://collectitude.wordpress.com>), the OpenAIRE portal (<https://www.OpenAIRE.eu/>) and ResearchGate platform (<https://www.researchgate.net/project/COLLECTITUDE-Building-the-collective-at-times-of-precarious-labour-and-its-counter-movements>).

2.2.3. Methods and/or software tools needed to access the data

Access to open data deposited in the project default repository (Zenodo) does not require any highly specialised method or software tool. The files can be downloaded from the repository via HTTP protocol using a standard web browser.

The software and tools for viewing, interpreting, or further processing the data files downloaded from the data repository depend on the type and format of the data (see Annex 1), but in general they will be available in common text or numeric format files (e.g. TXT, DOCX, XLSX, ODT, PDF, CSV, etc.). Whenever possible, data will be stored in format that can be opened with open source code and/or open source software (see 2.2.5).

2.2.4. Availability of documentation about the software needed to access the data

Documentation of software needed to access the data will be made available on the COLLECTITUDE website and data repository (Zenodo).

2.2.5 Availability of relevant software

COLLECTITUDE will not develop software, but will link to the available open source software that allows opening and processing the data – E.g. R for statistical analysis; QDA Miner Lite or RQDA for qualitative data analysis.

2.2.6. Where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

The default open access repository of the COLLECTITUDE project is **Zenodo**⁵, a certified repository which allows to deposit both publications and data, providing tools to link them, and ensures the following requirements:

- Persistent and unique identifiers (PIDs);
- Long term sustainability;
- Metadata;
- Curation and quality assurance;
- Free access;
- Security;
- Privacy;
- Common format;
- Provenance (maintaining a detailed logfile of changes to datasets and metadata).

Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon 2020, the EU Research and Innovation funding programme and OpenAIRE. A COLLECTITUDE project page has been set up at Zenodo for easy upload of project datasets (<https://zenodo.org/communities/collectitude/>).

Additionally, scientific publications will also be deposited in **RCAAP** – the Portuguese Common Repository⁶, designed to researchers affiliated institutions in the national scientific system who do not have their own institutional repository (as is the case of COLLECTITUDE host organisation, A3S)⁷.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org>

⁶ <http://comum.rcaap.pt>

⁷ Other repositories may also be considered such as the future 'Open Research Publishing Platform' of the European Commission and the 'European Open Science Cloud'.

2.2.7. How access will be provided in case there are any conditions/ restrictions

Where a restriction on open access to research data is necessary, attempts will be made to make data available under controlled conditions to other individual researchers. Details of restricted data will be included in the metadata, which is always publicly available in Zenodo.

Researchers wishing to request access to restricted data must provide a justification for how they fulfil the required conditions. Each new request will be evaluated for deciding on to either accept or reject the request. If the request is accepted, the requester receives a secret link which expires within 1-6 months.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1. Interoperability of project data

COLLECTITUDE project adheres to standards for formats (e.g. PDF or CSV), as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications (e.g. LibreOffice, R), in order to enhance data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc.

2.3.2. Data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies followed to facilitate interoperability

See 2.1.5 and 2.3.3.

2.3.3. Standard vocabulary for data types present in project datasets to allow interdisciplinary interoperability

Datasets produced by the project follow the widely used international standards of the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) for controlled vocabularies for the social, behaviour, and economic sciences (<https://ddialliance.org>), in particular the DDI Codebook v. 2.5, describing specific terms and rules for their use, in relation to, for instance, data source types, mode of collection, or general data formats, among others. In addition, they should be compatible with the Dublin Core metadata standard and thus can be interpreted by the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)⁸.

Full vocabularies and keywords used will be reported in future versions of the DMP and will integrate a glossary of terms for all COLLECTITUDE deliverables and outputs.

The use of these standards and the deposit of datasets in an interdisciplinary repository (Zenodo) facilitates the understanding and interdisciplinary interoperability of datasets.

⁸ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1. Licensing data to permit the widest reuse possible

Results of the action (such as data, figures, knowledge or information) are owned by the beneficiary that generates them (A3S), as per article 26 of the Grant Agreement. Nevertheless, open results arising from the COLLECTITUDE project will be released under a Creative Commons license (preferably Attribution 4.0 International - CC BY 4.0⁹), which provides a legal tool for permitting open access and re-use.

Regarding scientific publications, the choice on the publisher shall consider the possibility of authors to retain the copyright for their work and deposit the publication in an Open Access repository (according to 2.2.2).

2.4.2. When the data will be made available for re-use

Research data will be made available for re-use at the same time as the respective scientific publication is available as open access, that is:

- on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
- within twelve months of publication in any other case.

Details of when the publication and the data will become available will be included in the metadata (see 2.1.5) and made available at the same time as the publication.

2.4.3. Usability of the data produced and/or used in the project by third parties

Open results produced by the project and deposited in the selected repository (Zenodo) are usable by third parties after the end of the project. If confidentiality and personal data protection obligations related to specific research data forbid open access, the data may be deposited in a restricted repository and access may be granted upon request and under the conditions of a restricted license (see also 2.2.7).

2.4.4. Data quality assurance processes

Data quality assurance processes is an integral part of the whole research project and takes place at its various stages, involving different quality control measures:

(i) Before the data gathering

- Documenting the conceptualisation process and identification and operationalisation of main variables, based on the literature review;
- For each variable, the following information should be provided:

⁹ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

- The exact question wording or the exact meaning of the datum. Sources should be cited for questions drawn from previous surveys or published work;
 - The text of the question integrated into the variable text. If this is not possible, it is useful to have the item or questionnaire number (e.g., Question 3a), so that the archive can make the necessary linkages;
 - In case of variables constructed using other variables, details on how they were constructed, what decisions were made about imputations and weights.
- Conducting pre-tests of research instruments to uncover potential problems;
 - Initiate the process of documenting the entire workflow from the outset, so that it may be fully reproducible (TIER 2016; Bosman & Kramer 2018).

(ii) Data collection

- Using standardised methods and protocols for capturing observations, alongside recording forms with clear instructions;
- Writing a research journal to act as a retrospective check on reliability and validity and allow to reflect on ethical issues (see Iphofen 2015; Ortlipp 2008);
- Providing documentation on the data collection process, which is particularly relevant for allowing qualitative data to be used in secondary analysis. Any information that is necessary to fully exploit the analytic potential of the data and that provides context and clarity to a secondary user should be provided. Specifically, documentation for qualitative data should include (ICPSR 2010):
 - Project description, indicating its objectives and how the data articulate with related datasets. Publications providing essential information about the project should be cited.
 - Sample and sampling procedures, describing the target population investigated and the methods used to sample it. If available, a copy of the original sampling plan should be included as an appendix. A clear indication of the response rate should be presented, indicating the proportion of those sampled who actually participated in the study.
 - Research methods and practices (including the informed consent process) that are fully documented;
 - Data collection instruments such as interview and focus groups guides;
 - Blank copy of informed consent forms;
 - Details on selection of interview subjects;
 - Instructions followed by interviewers;
 - Details on setting of the data collection events (interviews/ focus groups) – persons or organizations responsible for data collection, date and geographic location of data production;

- Unit(s) of analysis/observation, describing who or what is being studied;
 - Flowchart of the data collection instrument – a graphical guide to the data, showing which respondents were asked which questions and how various items link to each other;
 - Any problems that arose during the selection and/or interview process and how they were handled.
- Information on secondary data source(s), indicating the original sources or documents from which data were obtained and describing how they were originally produced and why they have been included.

(iii) File creation (data entry and coding)

- For both quantitative or qualitative datasets, separating the coding and data-entry tasks as much as possible. Coding should be performed in such a way that distractions to coding tasks are minimized;
- Using controlled vocabularies, code lists and choice lists to minimise manual data entry. When possible, using software platforms that provide semi-automated annotation and coding;
- Following current conventions and best practices for coding in the social sciences (see Deterding & Waters, 2018);
- Provision of “coding instrument”, detailing the rules and definitions used for coding the data and exact meaning of codes. The documentation should show the interpretation of the codes assigned to each variable (for standard variables, such as occupation or industry, this information will appear in an appendix), as well as missing data codes¹⁰;
- List of abbreviations and other conventions – ideally variable names and variable labels should be standardized;
- Steps taken to remove direct identifiers in the data (e.g., name, address, etc.).

(iv) Data checking

- Double-checking coding of observations or responses and out-of-range values;
- Choosing random records for quality-control checks throughout the process;
- Statistical analyses such as frequencies, means, ranges or clustering to detect errors and anomalous values;
- Correcting errors made during transcription;
- Peer review.

(v) Data analysis

¹⁰ There are at least six different types of missing data which should have distinct codes: Refusal/ No answer; Don't know; Processing error; Not applicable; No match; No data available (see ICPSR 2010, p. 20).

- Using qualitative data analysis (QDA) software, in particular the memo/note function, to provide an “electronic audit trail” of the research process (Kapiszewski & Karcher 2019);
- Creating scripts for reproducible data analysis (e.g. SPSS syntax, R scripts), which may be posted to github and assigned a DOI number, enabling it to be cited;
- Imputation and editing information, in case of data that have been estimated or extensively edited;
- Accompanying notes and documentation about the data;
- Set up appropriate file structures and technical information on files (file formats, file linking, information on the location of variables in the data file);
- Back up data and documentation.

(vi) Data authenticity

- To be able to demonstrate the authenticity of data and to prevent unauthorised changes to data, best practice to ensure authenticity files (UK Data Service 2020) is to:
 - keep a single master file of data
 - assign responsibility for master files to a single project team member
 - regulate write access to master versions of data files
 - record all changes to master files
 - maintain old master files in case later ones contain errors
 - archive copies of master files at regular intervals
 - develop a formal procedure for the destruction of master.

(vii) Related publications

- Providing citations to publications based on the data;
- Providing a detailed methodological appendix to project publications.

2.4.5. Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

The open results that are deposited in the Zenodo repository will be available at least 5 years after the conclusion of the project. Furthermore, according to Zenodo’s retention period, “Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least”¹¹.

¹¹ Retrieved from <http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>.

3. Allocation of resources

3.1. Costs for making data FAIR

There are no immediate costs for making COLLECTITUDE research data FAIR (i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). Especially no costs are foreseen for storing open results in the project's default repository (Zenodo).

Providing open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications by publishing in green or gold open access journals may require payment of Article Processing Charges (APCs).

3.2. How open data costs will be covered

Any costs related to open access to research data and publications in H2020 are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project under the conditions defined in the Grant Agreement, and shall be covered by the project budget for Institutional costs.

3.3. Responsibilities for data management in the project

As part of the training and development of transferable and complementary skills foreseen by Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions – Individual Fellowships (MSCA-IF), responsibilities for data management in the project are assumed by the Experienced Researcher, supported by the staff of the project beneficiary and the supervisor.

The beneficiary (A3S) is responsible for applying for reimbursement for costs related to open access to research data and publications.

3.4. Costs and potential value of long-term preservation

No immediate costs are foreseen for long-term preservation of open data stored in the Zenodo repository.

4. Data security

4.1. Provisions for data security

Provisions for data security have been defined in Deliverable 1.5 on data protection procedures. Personal, sensitive or confidential data will not be deposited in repositories, nor disclosed to third parties.

The choice for Zenodo for depositing and storing data has been based on the strong security measures of the repository¹², which include:

- Storing of two replicas of each file copy located on different disk servers;
- Physical access to data centres is restricted to a limited number of staff with appropriate training and who have been granted access in line with their professional duties;
- Servers managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers, meaning e.g. remote access to our servers are restricted to Zenodo staff with appropriate training, and the operating system and installed applications are kept updated with latest security patches via our automatic configuration management system Puppet;
- Running of host and network based intrusion detection systems and monitoring of traffic flow, pattern and contents to detect attacks;
- Cryptographic password storing.

4.2. Safe storing of data in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation

Zenodo is an OpenAIRE's trusted repository¹³.

Data deposited in the Zenodo are safely stored for long time preservation, for the lifetime of the repository (defined for at least the next 20 years).

5. Ethical aspects

All currently identified ethical aspects of the COLLECTITUDE project have been addressed in the ethics deliverables of the project, in line with the EU key ethical principles and research codes of conduct, as well as the current regulations on Data Protection:

D1.1 - Procedures to identify/recruit research participants;

D1.2 – Approval by the ethics committee;

D1.3 – Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR);

D1.4 – Provision of informed consent forms and information sheets;

D1.5 – Data Protection Procedures;

¹² See <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

¹³ See <https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo/>.

D1.6 – Appointment of a Data Protection Officer (DPO);

D1.7 – Informed consent procedures in regard to data processing.

Informed consent forms will include a clause regarding data sharing and long-term preservation in order to allow open data.

6. Other

Currently, the project does not make use of other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management.

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Annexes

Annex I. Data Inventory Table

WP	Dataset	Type of data	Data source	Origin of the data (method of collection)	Data format	Expected levels of accessibility
1	Literature report with conceptual framework	Qualitative/ Quantitative	Secondary	Review of relevant scientific and secondary literature; Development of a glossary of COLLECTITUDE concepts	Text	Open
1	Datasets (Eurostat data, Labour Force Survey, European Working Conditions Survey, data from the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics – INE).	Quantitative	Secondary	Review of relevant statistics	Numeric	Open
1	Exploratory interviews to key informants	Qualitative	Primary	Open ended interviews	Text notes	Restricted
1	Factsheet of project Variables & Indicators	Qualitative/ Quantitative	Primary/ Secondary	Collection of knowledge from project team; Review of relevant scientific and secondary literature and Exploratory interviews	Text	Open
1	Interview guide	Qualitative	Primary/ Secondary	Collection of knowledge from project team; Review of relevant scientific and secondary literature and Exploratory interviews	Text	Open
1	Focus group guide	Qualitative	Primary/ Secondary	Collection of knowledge from project team; Review of relevant scientific and secondary literature and Exploratory interviews	Text	Open
1	Field notes template	Qualitative	Primary/ Secondary	Collection of knowledge from project team; Review of relevant scientific and secondary	Text	Open

				literature and Exploratory interviews		
2	Observation field notes	Qualitative	Primary	Raw field notes and photographs taken by the project researchers	Text Images	Restricted
2	Semi-structured Interviews	Qualitative	Primary	Raw data from the interviews conducted by project researchers	Audio recordings Text transcripts	Restricted
2	Content analysis of interviews	Qualitative	Primary	Results from the analysis of interviews	Text	Open
2	Peer-reviewed scientific paper	Qualitative	Primary	Collection of knowledge from project team; Review of relevant scientific and secondary literature and interviews	Text Numeric	Open
3	Dataset of press and social media news	Qualitative	Primary	Collection of press and social media news by project researchers	Text	Open
3	Content analysis of press and social media news	Qualitative	Primary	Results from the analysis press and social media news	Text	Open
3	Focus Groups	Qualitative	Primary	Raw data from the Focus Groups conducted by project researchers	Audio recordings Text transcripts	Restricted
3	Content analysis of Focus Groups	Qualitative	Primary	Results from the analysis of Focus Groups	Text	Open
3	Peer-reviewed scientific paper	Qualitative	Primary	Analysis of project primary data; collection of knowledge from project team; review of relevant scientific and secondary literature	Text Numeric	Open
4	Report to stakeholders	Qualitative	Primary	Analysis of project primary data; collection of knowledge from project team; review of relevant scientific and secondary literature	Text	Open
4	Peer-reviewed scientific paper	Qualitative	Primary	Analysis of project primary data; collection of	Text Numeric	Open

				knowledge from project team; review of relevant scientific and secondary literature		
4	Final analytical matrix	Qualitative	Primary	Analysis of project primary data; collection of knowledge from project team; review of relevant scientific and secondary literature	Text	Open
4	Project final report	Qualitative	Primary	Analysis of project primary data; collection of knowledge from project team; review of relevant scientific and secondary literature	Text	Open